

Seed treatment to maintain viability, vigor, and yield potential of stored rice seed

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Rice seed deteriorate significantly under ordinary uncontrolled storage in eastern India, especially during the warm and humid monsoon months from June to September. Studies at the Calcutta University College of Agriculture over the past 5 years have led to the development of a simple and easily practiced soaking-drying method of seed treatment to maintain vigor, viability, and productivity. Before stored seed begin to lose viability (5–10 months, depending on ambient conditions), they are soaked in double their volume of water or dilute solutions of sodium phosphate (dibasic, 10^{-4} M) for 5 hours and then dried back to their original weight in the sun or in a current of hot air (36–38°C) in a drying cabinet. The treatment greatly minimized the subsequent deterioration of such seeds when restored under ambient conditions (see table).

With fresh seed, the soaking-drying treatment is ineffective and would even accelerate deterioration when seed are stored for longer periods. But the treatment would break the dormancy of freshly harvested seed of certain cultivars

Effect of different physiochemical seed treatments on germination and yield of rice.^a University of Calcutta, India.

Treatment ^b	Germination ^c (%)	Mean root length after 120 h (mm)	Mean shoot length after 120 h (mm)	Grain yield ^d (t/ha)
Control	68 b	52 b	15 b	4.6 c
Water	88 a	62 a	23 a	6.1 b
Sodium phosphate (dibasic, 10^{-4} M)	91 a	66 a	25 a	6.7 a

^aIn any column, means that are followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bNine-month-old Ratna seed, which had been stored under ambient conditions (RH $67 \pm 11\%$, temp. $27.1 \pm 4^\circ\text{C}$), were treated on 22 Aug. 1976 and were subsequently sown in Dec. 1976.

^cGermination tests were conducted in the laboratory at 28°C before sowing in the seedbed on 21 Dec. 1976.

^dYield of crop at 135 days' duration (sowing to transplanting, 40 days; transplanting to harvest, 95 days); differences in field (nursery) emergence of seedlings were eliminated during transplanting.

and give more uniform germination of seed that are immediately planted. Treatment of old, deteriorating seed is not advisable. The marginal effects of presowing treatment of stored seeds imply the necessity of maintaining a sufficient time gap between treatment and planting.

Hydration has also been achieved by spraying or dipping the stored seed in water or chemical solutions for a few minutes and then keeping them in shade 2–3 hours before drying. Even equilibrating the moisture of stored seed with a saturated atmosphere (100% RH) for 24 hours, then drying them back,

would greatly reduce seed deterioration in subsequent storage. Drying back to the original weight is important; storage of partially dried seed would do more harm than good. Seed that have been treated can be re-treated several months later to further extend their storage life.

The treatments have been effective in all rice cultivars so far studied: Ratna, Jaya, IR8, Pusa 2-21, Mahsuri, Rupsail, Patnai 23, Sitabhog, Dular, and Dhairal. The method could be used to maintain germplasm collections under ordinary storage conditions for a considerable period, and eliminates the need to regrow the genetic stocks each year. **W**

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Varietal reaction to *Podredumbre de la Vaim* (*Ophiobolus* sp.) in Lambayeque, Peru

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Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of the varieties Nylamp, Chicama, Minabir, Inti, IR8, Siam Garden, Mochica, and Chancay were inoculated with a mycelium suspension of *Ophiobolus* sp in such a way that the mycelium was in contact with the sheaths. The plants were then

kept in a greenhouse for 2 months. Adequate humidity was provided by irrigating the plants as needed. The presence or absence of typical disease symptoms and fungus structures was then evaluated.

The sheaths of Nylamp, Mochica, and Siam Garden varieties were all infected but Chicama, Minabit, and Chancay had only 25% sheath infection. Inti and IR8 were infected least, suggesting varietal resistance to the disease in Lambayeque state, Peru. **W**

Varietal reaction to kresek infection

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Kresek is normally observed 1 to 4 weeks after transplanting. Adult plants may also be infected if conditions are favorable for the disease and if the variety is susceptible. Under experimental conditions, young seedlings are infected more than older seedlings.